

Student Perception and Experience with "Talk" - AI-Powered Speaking Partner Application

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Abstract: *Based on the conclusions made on how students felt about using "TALK" as a medium for English language study. Pupils gave positive feedback on using "TALK" as a platform for speaking instruction. The kids thought "TALK" was entertaining, stimulating, thrilling, and enjoyable. In addition, it makes pupils more eager to play it. Additionally, "TALK" has a wide variety of texts that facilitate pupils' use of common English. The research indicates that the "TALK" application can effectively contribute to students' speaking development. The study reveals that students express favorable sentiments regarding the use of Quizizz for online assessments. Additionally, they express a desire for other educators to employ "TALK" for assessing their students' speaking skills. Given the novelty of this application in the field, there is a significant research gap, prompting the researcher to recommend that future scholars explore and investigate the potential of the "TALK" application*

Keywords: TALK, Students' Perception, AI-Powered

INTRODUCTION

English, as the language used in the realm of international communication, has increasingly become a prerequisite and a benchmark to determine whether someone is considered capable of mastering the understanding of the global world or not (Mukminin et al., 2019). An individual's proficiency level in the English language now serves as a fundamental guide to assess their credibility across various fields, ranging from education, business, economics, even to politics and science (Muniroh et al., 2023). This phenomenon is not hard to find, and one barometer is the growing number of job vacancies that require applicants to achieve a certain level of English proficiency before being recruited into a company.

Another example is evident in the field of education. A student that aspiring to pursue higher studies is greatly influenced by their English language abilities. A student may receive scholarship opportunities or other conveniences, based on their proficiency in English. Particularly in countries such as Indonesia, where English is still considered a foreign language, with less than 40% of the population proficient in English (Rukmi & Khasanah, 2020). The English Proficiency Index of 2022 that is released by EF Education First ranked Indonesia at the number of 81 from 111 countries assessed for their population's English language skills. Consequently, with these facts, English proficiency in Indonesia is still perceived as a rarity for the majority of the population.

This fact highlights the increasing need for effective and accessible English education. Many schools and educational institutions are now developing modern and innovative methods for teaching English, encompassing both teaching approaches and tools that facilitate learners

in enhancing their English language skills (Cong-Lem, 2018). In learning English, there are four essential competencies that must be mastered by the learners. These four competencies are proficiency in reading, listening, writing, and speaking (Pliushchenko & Zaslavskiy, 2021). However, the speaking skill is often considered as the most crucial among the other four abilities. Speaking is one of the most important skills of all four language skills, because individuals who learn a language are referred to as the speakers of that language. The main aim of English language teaching is to give learners the ability to use English language effectively and correctly in communication (Jarrín & Kim, 2019).

Speaking is a fundamental aspect of language acquisition, serving as a pivotal skill that can be honed through the deliberate expansion of one's vocabulary. It is a dynamic process encompassing the art of constructing and articulating meaning through the proficient utilization of words and non-verbal cues within various contexts (Constrained et al., 2019). In essence, speaking is a multifaceted act that transcends the mere vocalization of words. The mastery of speaking skills necessitates a comprehensive understanding of the cultural and social dimensions that influence language use.

However, from this speaking ability, there is one crucial element known as oral proficiency. English oral proficiency refers to an individual's ability to communicate effectively in spoken English. It involves the skill of expressing oneself clearly, fluently, and appropriately in oral communication (Vančová, 2022). Individuals often seek to improve their English oral proficiency for personal and professional development, because English oral proficiency is a crucial aspect of language competence, in both social and professional contexts.

Thus, with the advancement of technology, there are currently numerous tools and applications that are designed to facilitate students in improving their English speaking skills (Chun et al., 2016). One of these tools is called TALK. TALK is an online platform which is designed to help users improve their spoken English skills. It utilizes advanced speech recognition technology to provide users with feedback on their pronunciation, intonation, and overall spoken language proficiency (Mayor, 2021).

In this research, the researchers aim to explore students' perceptions regarding the use of “TALK” as one of the tools or media integrated into their speaking learning. Ardies, De Maeyer, Gijbels, and van Keulen (2014) argued that perceptions and attitudes towards any educational technology could be used to measure whether or not this technology has positive or negative impacts on the environment.

LITERATURE REVIEW

PERCEPTION

In order to give their surroundings meaning, people organize and interpret their sensory impressions through the process of perception. This is according to Walgito's (2013) statement that the process of sensing—also known as the sensory process—occurs before perception and is the act of an individual receiving a stimulus through their senses.

Rakhmat (2004) mentioned in his book *Psychology of Communication* that perception is an experience gained through information collection and message interpretation regarding the subject of events or interactions. It implies that the awareness of things, activities,

and relationships can be defined as perception. obtained by interpreting the message and drawing conclusions from the data.

Every human being was made uniquely. since every person has unique perceptions. Disagreements between personalities, whether they stem from similarities or dislikes, are always based on the individual's response to the object in his or her field of vision. Aristotle asserted that perception is connected to a change in the sense organ, which is brought about by the object of experience (Knutilla & Karkainen, 2008).

Perceptions come in two types: positive and negative. Self-perception needs to be reflected in all of one's individual acts, as well as in one's own thoughts and physical manifestations. It is also brought on by other people's reactions. Every person's behaviors and decisions throughout life are influenced by their perspective (Burns et al., 2017).

E-Learning

The rapid growth of information and communication technology in the twenty-first century has increased the usage of digital media for a wide range of professional applications in both official and informal education. Technology devices have a big part in helping teachers and students make the most of technology, according to Kumar Basak et al. (2018). The method of using technology in the learning process is called e-learning. The benefits of e-learning for students are various. It can get better, particularly if used in English classrooms. This is correlated by Cai (2012) AI, who claimed that e-learning modifies pedagogical approaches and eventually increases the effectiveness of teaching and learning through the use of computers and the Internet. Students cannot learn a language; they are only competent at passing tests if we insist on teaching grammar and vocabulary. In thirty years, the younger generation will still not be content with schooling if we do not

make changes. Language proficiency is a type of mental skill that requires the appropriate training techniques and instructional approaches. In addition to relieving teachers of most of their labor, e-learning will make it simple for pupils to acquire English.

TALK APPLICATION

“Talk English Speaking Practice” is a free application that helps you improve your English speaking skills. This app has various features to help you learn and practice speaking English include Interactive Conversation Lesson then Conversations with Native Speakers and the last features is Quizzes and Games

In this application there are many themes related to everyday life, therefore it really helps users so they can learn and immediately practice them in real life.

Dimas Vega RPB, Pramana Raffif, Abdullah Yusuf, Ahmad Syafi'i
Student Perception and Experience with "Talk"

not only does it provide lots of conversations, but in the application we not only learn about speaking but also focus on listening because in this application there are native people who will help us on how to pronounce a sentence well and correctly

After hearing the native speaker's conversation, the user is asked first to do a quiz so that the user feels they understand what the native speaker was talking about

and then finally the great thing about this application is that after the user feels they understand how the native speaks and understands what is being said, the last part of this application is practice in pronunciation so there are 2 sessions where the user will role play as the one in the conversation. practice: The user will be trained first regarding speed in speaking English, which is adjusted to the application, then secondly, recording, namely the user is asked to record your voice.

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a descriptive-qualitative research. the goal of this study is to finding out the students' perception of the use of TALK as learning tool platform in teaching English specifically for speaking. The participants of this study were 4 students. The main instruments employed in this research are an online questionnaire and indepth interview. The quantitative data were statistically analyzed. qualitative data were analyzed and presented thematically

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

QUESTIONNAIRE RESULT

Based on the results of the questionnaire above, it can be interpreted that the "TALK" application is quite user-friendly by showing a fairly high presentation, as indicated by the positive responses regarding its ease of use, intuitive interface, and overall user experience. The application's user-friendly design contributes to a smoother and more enjoyable learning process, allowing learners to navigate through the features and functionalities with ease, access relevant resources, and engage in productive language practice sessions.

This shows that more than 75% of them said that "talk" really helps them improve their English speaking skills over, highlighting the belief that regular conversation and practice play a vital role in enhancing language proficiency.

According to the data above, half of the respondents strongly agreed when they said that when using the "talk" application it was very helpful in identifying speaking errors from respondents

According to the data above we can see 50% informant agree if "Talk" is a useful tool for practicing speaking in a foreign language , it is explained that although the "talk" application is quite helpful for them in English pronunciation, the results show that they are not sure that "talk" can be a quite useful tool in practicing speaking English.

Based on the results 50% informant agree with this statement, it shows that in the "talk" application the language trained is very realistic with the language commonly used every day indicating that the platform effectively simulates real-life conversations, exposing learners to authentic vocabulary, idiomatic expressions, and natural speech patterns that are essential for effective communication in various social and professional contexts.

According to data with an average of 3.25 , 'talk' can help increase their confidence in talking to appropriate targets allowing them to practice their language skills in real-time conversations and gradually overcome any hesitation or self-doubt that may arise when communicating with native speakers or individuals in specific professional or social settings.

in this data we see that the number for this point is very high with a percentage more then 75% they agreed that learning variations in dialects and accents in the "talk" application could help them adapt it directly to real life.

According to the informants, on average they agreed that the use of the "talk" application had increased the informants' fluency in the target language. This positive feedback shows that this application has been quite effective in facilitating language practice and communication, thereby improving language skills among informants.

From all the informants, they strongly agreed that the "talk" application was very enjoyable as an English learning tool for them. This highlights the application's ability to engage and motivate the informants, making the language learning process a pleasurable and immersive experience. The positive perception of the "talk" application as an enjoyable tool further emphasizes its effectiveness in enhancing the informants' English language skills.

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Based on the data above, the informants gave quite low scores, namely with an average point of 2, where the informants agreed that the language in the "Talk" application did not match their current skills. When they tried this "talk" application they faced quite a complicated problem, namely the language used in this application was quite difficult for users to understand, therefore they felt that in terms of language it was not up to the user's abilities.

Of all the informants, an average of 80 percent of people said that after they used this "talk" application, most of them were very motivated to speak the target language they wanted

From several informants, they said that for all the features in this application, it is quite recommended to other people. The informants highlighted the application's robust security measures, intuitive user interface, seamless cross-platform compatibility, and extensive customization options as key factors that make it highly recommended

According to the results of the data, they said that the "Talk" application is a very good additional learning resource for their speaking learning apart from the lessons at school.

Most of the informants said that after they used this "talk" application they felt that their speaking in the target language had improved quite a lot, one of the factors was because they used this application quite often.

most of the informants said that when using the "talk" application they felt that when speaking their target language the language conveyed was very structured and organized They praised the application's intelligent language models and speech recognition capabilities, which helped them formulate coherent sentences and express their ideas clearly

from the many questions we asked in the questionnaire, most of the informants said that the "talk" application made them feel satisfied and quite happy with the application Overall, their positive feedback and satisfaction with the 'talk' application reflect its value as a reliable and effective tool for language learning

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The results of this study indicate that students see the employment of "TALK" as a speaking tool for part of their education favorably. A positive outlook is a beautiful gift that equips one to engage with the world, persevere through challenges, and put other people's needs ahead of one's own 21. It promotes establishing connections and devoting oneself to others.

The research indicates that students' Several opinions on the employment of "TALK" as a speaking tool for part of their education can be attributed

to a number of factors. They all concurred that "TALK" was fascinating and thrilling to start.

They all agreed that "TALK" was very interesting and stressful at first but after they studied it further they felt that this application was very interesting and helped them in learning English

the next reason is because this application is quite motivating for users in their speaking learning with features that really help them in learning so that they feel confident enough to implement it around them.

CONCLUSION

Based on the conclusions made on how students felt about using "TALK" as a medium for English language study. Pupils gave positive feedback on using "TALK" as a platform for speaking instruction. The kids thought "TALK" was entertaining, stimulating, thrilling, and enjoyable. In addition, it makes pupils more eager to play it. Additionally, "TALK" has a wide variety of texts that facilitate pupils' use of common English. The research indicates that the "TALK" application can effectively contribute to students' speaking development. The study reveals that students express favorable sentiments regarding the use of Quizizz for online assessments. Additionally, they express a desire for other educators to employ "TALK" for assessing their students' speaking skills. Given the novelty of this application in the field, there is a significant research gap, prompting the researcher to recommend that future scholars explore and investigate the potential of the "TALK" application.

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